

Module 3	Cloud Data Environment (CDE)
Course coordinator	Ruggero Lot (RL)
Lecturers	Gianfranco Gallizia and RL
Class duration	21 hours
Module Description	Introduction of cloud computing infrastructures in the framework of data analysis. Students will be introduced to the main concepts related to Cloud Computing, and they will be able to experience the installation, configuration and usage of a cloud infrastructure and discussing how to use them proficiently to deploy simple applications in data related applications.
Main topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction to Virtual Machine and Containers. - docker / docker compose / docker file - podman - Networking container - AWS
Objectives	On successful completion of this module students should have the basic skills to operate in a cloud environment, to setup and configure their own scientific environment, and to use them proficiently to deploy simple applications in data related applications.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Many resources online available